

ELECTRODEPOSITION OF CADMIUM ON IRON.

BY DUSHYANT NARASINGASA SOLANKI AND BHASKAR GOVIND JOSHI.

Results are given for the optimum conditions for the production of a smooth and adherent deposit of cadmium on iron in respect of inter-electrode distance, the electrolyte concentration, the current density, the duration of electrolysis, the temperature, proportion of free sulphuric acid and of sodium sulphate. Data are also given for the cathode efficiency in respect of cadmium deposition under the influence of the above factors and that of the addition of a large number of inorganic and organic agents in different proportions, e.g., stannous chloride, aluminium sulphate, dextrin, gelatin, etc. The possible rôle of these addition agents is also discussed in the light of the current theories.

The coating of cadmium is superior to that of zinc for protecting iron and steel as it is less susceptible to atmospheric corrosion. In contrast to the dull appearance of zinc it is white and lustrous, almost like silver. These and the like were some of the remarkable properties of cadmium, which attracted the attention of the metallurgist. A review of the literature shows that much of the work on cadmium deposition is restricted to the use of double cyanide solutions, which are, however, unstable and therefore, apt to undergo decomposition; this leads to many practical difficulties in maintaining the satisfactory control of the plating bath. The work of Mary Dover (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **33**, 1577) and of Mary Holmes and Mary Dover (*ibid.*, 1910, **32**, 1251) has shown that cadmium can be deposited in a satisfactory and adhesive form from various organic electrolytes, viz., lactate, acetate, formate, etc., by using a rotating spiral anode, under conditions of (a) low current, and (b) decidedly acidic medium. It was observed that each of the above electrolytes exerted a marked and specific influence on the character of the deposit; the best deposits were obtained in presence of a mixture of ions and especially of SO_4^{2-} ion. A detailed account of the various baths for cadmium deposition is found in an exhaustive review by Mathers and Marble (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1914, **25**, 297, 319). Their results show that alkaline and ammoniacal tartrate baths give very loose and spongy deposits. The baths containing the sulphates and chlorides, when used singly, did not give satisfactory results, though the latter yielded satisfactory deposits especially in the presence of NH_4Cl , free HCl and suitable addition agent. Excellent results were also obtained from solutions of fluoride, silicofluoride, borofluoride (*cf.* also Millian, *Bull. soc. chim. Belg.*, 1925, **34**, 143) and perchlorate (*cf.* Müller and Barchmann, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1933, **39**, 341) in presence of free acid and suitable addition

agent. With the exception of the work by Wernick (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1932, 62, 75) the information available in the literature on the quantitative data for cadmium deposition is very meagre. In the present investigation an attempt has, therefore, been made to study the deposition of cadmium on iron quantitatively in regard to the influence of a number of factors (*vide infra*).

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

The electrolysis was carried out in a round glass trough, about 2½" deep, and having a capacity of about 200 c.c. kept immersed in a thermostat and maintained at the desired temperature. The temperature of the bath solution was controlled within $\pm 0.2^\circ$. The anode used was a well cleaned thick plate of pure cadmium of size 4 × 4 cm. A thin plate (4 × 3.5 cm. approx.) serving as the cathode was first rendered free from grease by dipping it in a hot 10% caustic soda solution for a few minutes and then washing it with water; it was next immersed in moderately strong nitric acid to remove surface scales and rust and to loosen the coating of carbon. It was then well washed with water and was made an anode in the etching solution (100 g. H_2SO_4 and 100 g. Na_2SO_4 in 1000 c.c. water) and current was passed for half an hour. The plate was made an anode to prevent it from becoming brittle owing to the occlusion of hydrogen evolved at the cathode. This gave an uniformly etched and bright surface. The plate was then washed with distilled water and finally with alcohol, dried and weighed accurately. A copper coulometer was used to give the measure of the quantity of electricity passed through the electrolyte; the coulometer solution was prepared according to Ottel's recommendations (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1893, 17, 543). The current was obtained from storage cells; the circuit included an electrolytic bath, copper coulometer, a precision type ammeter, and an adjustable resistance in series and voltmeter, connected across the electrodes in the bath.

The stock solution of 8% cadmium was prepared by dissolving 182.5 g. of Merck's pure cadmium sulphate, $CdSO_4 \cdot 8/3H_2O$, in 1000 c.c. of distilled water. In all the following experiments this stock solution was used either alone or after proper dilution or with the appropriate additions of the other materials used in this work. The concentration of cadmium sulphate in the solutions used, is expressed, for the sake of convenience, in terms of the metal content only. To investigate the optimum conditions for a smooth, bright and adherent deposit of cadmium, the influence of the following factors has been studied over ranges :

	Optimum values.
(a) Inter-electrode distance, 3 to 6.5 cm.	6 cm.
(b) Concentration of cadmium sulphate, 8 to 2% Cd.	4% Cd.
(c) Current density, 1.75 to 11.56 amp./ft ² .	5 amp./ft ² .
(d) Time, 10 to 60 min.	20 minutes.
(e) Free sulphuric acid, N/50 to N/4.	N/50 acid.
(f) Sodium sulphate, 1 to 10%.	5% Na ₂ SO ₄

The influence of C.D. and temperature on the nature and quantity of the deposit has been studied in a greater detail. Measurements were made of the cathode efficiency for the Cd-deposition at 30° under these conditions and in the presence of (i) inorganic agents, viz., Al₂(SO₄)₃, 18H₂O; NiSO₄, 7H₂O; H₂O₂; ZnSO₄, 7H₂O; HgCl₂; CrO₃; SnCl₂; SnO; SnO₂ and traces of SnCl₄, BiCl₃; (ii) organic agents, viz., sucrose, glycerine, dextrin, gelatin and traces of carbon disulphide and pyridine. The nature of the cadmium deposit obtained in each of these experiments is also recorded, as examined with a microscope. The cathode efficiency in any given experiment was calculated by the relation,

$$\% \text{ Cathode efficiency} = \frac{100 \times \text{equiv. wt. of Cu} \times \text{wt. of Cd deposited}}{\text{Equiv. wt. of Cd} \times \text{wt. of Cu (coulometer) deposited}}$$

TABLE IA.

Variation of inter-electrode distance.

Conc. = 8% Cd as sulphate. Temp. = 25°. C. D. = 10 amps./sq. ft.
Time = 20 min.

Electrode distance	Nature of the deposit.
3 cm.	Deposit fine, non-adhesive and gets washed off easily; 'tree' forming tendency at the edges.
5.0	Deposit finer, 'tree' forming tendency at the edges, non-adhesive but shining.
6.0	Deposit still finer and adherent, very fine crystals, no 'tree' formation.
6.5	Do.

TABLE IB.

Variation of concentration of the electrolyte (CdSO₄).

Temp. = 25°. C. D. = 5.5 amps./sq. ft. Inter-electrode distance = 6 cm.
Time = 20 min.

Conc. of CdSO ₄	Nature of the deposit.
8% Cd	Irregular crystals, fine and shining.
4	Regular and smooth crystals; deposit uniform and fine grained though adherence was not satisfactory.
2	Deposit shining and lustrous; 'tree' forming tendency at the edges.

TABLE IC.

Variation of current density.

Conc. = 4% Cd as sulphate. Temp. = 25°. Inter-electrode distance = 6 cm.

Time = 20 min.

C. D. per sq. ft.	Nature of the deposit.
1.75 amp.	Deposit crystalline, shining but granular with deep holes.
3.66	Improvement in structure.
5.64	Deposit very fine, regular crystals; much improvement in structure.
7.73	Do.
9.43	Improvement in structure, but 'tree' formation at the edges.
11.56	Do.

TABLE ID.

Variation with time.

Conc. = 4% Cd as sulphate. C. D. = 5 amp./sq. ft. Inter-electrode distance = 6 cm. Temp. = 25°. The same bath solution used for all expts.

Time.	Nature of the deposit.
10 min.	Deposit shining and lustrous, fine-grained and of uniform structure.
15	Do.
20	Slight improvement.
30	Do.
60	Deposit shows tendency to become spongy, powdery and black from the commencement of the electrolysis. The deposit being non-adherent, falls to powder on mere tapping the plate.

TABLE IE.

Effect of addition of free sulphuric acid to the bath.

Conc. = 4% Cd as sulphate. C. D. = 5 amp./sq. ft. Inter-electrode distance = 6 cm. Temp. = 30°.

Conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Nature of the deposit.	% Cathode efficiency of Cd.
0	...	96.49 } 98.24 } 97.37
N/50	Deposit white, lustrous, crystalline, granular & coarse with little pitting effect.	93.89 } 94.21 } 94.05
N/20	Do.	90.46 } 85.44 } 89.7
N/10	Less uniform, increased pitting effect.	68.24 } 68.85 } 68.55
N/4	Deposit bad with deep holes and cracks	25.07 } 24.72 } 24.89

TABLE I.

Effect of the addition of sodium sulphate.

Bath composition = 4% Cd as $\text{CdSO}_4 + N/50 \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Time = 20 min.
 Inter-electrode distance = 6 cm. Temp. = 30°. C. D. = 5 amp./sq. ft.

Na_2SO_4 .	Nature of the deposit.	% Cathode efficiency of Cd.
1%	Deposit white, lustrous but irregular with pitting effect; adherence poor.	91'77 } 91'71 } 91'74
2.5	Deposit lustrous, regular and adherent; pitting effect less.	92'42 } 92'77 } 92'60
5.0	Deposit much improved in structure being regular and uniform; very little pitting effect.	96'70 } 96'92 } 96'86
10'	Do. No marked improvement.	97'44 } 98'56 } 98'0

TABLE II.

Effect of current density.

Bath soln. = 4% Cd as $\text{CdSO}_4 + N/50\text{-H}_2\text{S}()_4 + 5\% \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4$.
 Inter-electrode distance = 6 cm. Temp. = 30°. Time = 20 min.

C. D. per sq. ft.	Wt. of Cd deposit.	Wt. of Cu (coulometer deposit).	% Cathode efficiency (mean).	Remarks.
1.0 amp	0.0451 g. 0.0328	0.0278 g. 0.0204	91'77 } 90'95 } 91'37	Deposit adherent but dull and not regular.
5.0	0.0787 0.0730	0.0458 0.0426	96'70 } 96'92 } 96'81	Deposit adherent, lustrous & uniformly fine-grained.
10.0	0.1196 0.0898	0.0695 0.0521	97'34 } 97'50 } 97'42	Fine-grained & lustrous deposit but non-adherent with 'tree' formation at the edges.
15.0	0.1273 0.1482	0.0733 0.0840	98'22 } 99'79 } 99'01	Do.

TABLE III.

Effect of temperature.

Bath soln. = 4% Cd as $\text{CdSO}_4 + N/50\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4 + 5\% \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4$. Inter-electrode distance = 6 cm. C. D. = 5 amps./sq. ft. Time = 20 min.

Temp.	Wt. of Cd deposit.	Wt. of Cu (coulometer deposit).	% Cathode efficiency of Cd.	Remarks.
10°	0·0646 g.	0·0407 g.	89·78	} 89·60 Deposit adherent, regular & fine grained; pitting effect very little.
	0·0600	0·0380	89·32	
20°	0·0554	0·0339	92·43	} 92·77 Do.
	0·0541	0·0329	93·01	
30°	0·0781	0·0458	96·70	} 96·81 Deposit uniformly lustrous, regular & adherent with very little crevices.
	0·0730	0·0426	96·02	
45°	0·0700	0·0406	97·52	} 97·65 Do. little pitting effect.
	0·0574	0·0332	97·79	
60°	0·0652	0·0387	95·28	} 95·32 Deposit not uniform, less adherent but bright with crevices.
	0·0767	0·0455	95·35	
80°	0·0603	0·0356	93·76	} 93·41 Do. deep crevices
	0·0556	0·0338	93·05	

TABLE IV.

Effect of addition agent.

Bath soln. = 4% Cd as sulphate + $N/50 \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + 5\% \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4$.

Inter-electrode distance = 6 cm. Time = 20 min.

Temp. = 30°. C.D. = 5 amp./sq. ft.

Addition agent. (A)	Amount of (A) in 100 c.c. soln.	Wt. of Cd. deposit.	Wt. of Cu (coulometer).	% Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.
$\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3, 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0·25 g.	0·0590 g.	0·0345 g.	96·74	} 96·49 Fine-grained and white deposit but not lustrous and adherent.
"	"	0·0553	0·0325	96·23	
"	0·5	0·0561	0·0329	96·45	} 96·19 Deposit finer and better than in previous reading.
"	"	0·0541	0·0320	95·63	
"	"	0·0582	0·0341	96·51	

TABLE IV (contd.)

Addition agent. (A)	Amount of (A) in 100 c.c. solu.	Wt. of Cd. deposit.	Wt. of Cu (coulo- meter).	%Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.
$\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3, 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.0 g.	0.0738 g.	0.0436 g.	95.74	} 95.70 Deposit improved in all respects.
"	"	0.0504	0.0298	95.66	
"	1.5	0.0744	0.0439	95.86	} 95.56 Still further improved but slight blackening effect.
"	"	0.0755	0.0449	95.26	
$\text{NiSO}_4, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.1	0.0574	0.0343	94.64	} 94.93 Improvement in the deposit in all respects.
"	"	0.0616	0.0366	95.22	
"	0.2	0.0608	0.0364	94.47	} 94.55 Do.
"	"	0.0604	0.0361	94.63	
"	0.5	0.0759	0.0459	93.53	} 93.26 Still improved.
"	"	0.0485	0.0295	92.99	
HgCl_2	0.1	...	...	...	Black, powdery and non-adherent deposit.
CrO_3	0.2	...	...	...	Do.
CS_2	1 drop	...	...	...	Do.
Pyridine	1 drop	...	...	91.17	} 91.11 Deposit shining uniform, irregular and granular.
				91.06	
$\text{ZnSO}_4, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.1 g	0.0516	0.0306	95.38	} 95.59 No distinct improvement.
"	"	0.0490	0.0289	95.8	
"	0.5	0.0560	0.0332	95.4	} 95.27 Irregular, granular and crystalline deposit with diseased spots.
"	"	0.0360	0.0214	95.15	
H_2O_2	0.1 c.c.	0.0506	0.0309	92.62	} 92.4 Deposit non-uniform, lustrous, granular in structure with deep crevices.
"	"	0.0585	0.0359	92.17	
"	0.5	0.0596	0.0345	97.68	} 97.97 Deposit irregular and less satisfactory; worse than in previous case.
"	"	0.0597	0.0344	98.17	
SnCl_2	0.009 g.	0.0849	0.0499	96.23	} 97.15 Deposit uniform shining and adherent.
"	"	0.0629	0.0363	98.07	
"	0.1	0.0759	0.0436	98.46	} 99.1 Deposit white amorphous and uniform; no pitting effect; no crevices, very good deposit.
"	0.11	0.0573	0.0327	99.13	
"	"	0.0613	0.0350	99.09	Do. Deposit very satisfactory.

TABLE IV (contd.).

Addition agent. (A)	Amount of (A) in 100 c.c. soln.	Wt. of Cd. deposit.	Wt. of Cu (coulom- eter).	%Cathode efficiency.	Remarks.
SnO	0.1 g.	0.0549 g	0.0327 g.	94.97	Granular, crystalline and coarse deposit with deep crevices and diseased spots.
"	"	0.0537	0.0317	95.8	
SnO ₂	0.1	0.0484	0.0284	96.38	Do. Structure somewhat better than in the previous case.
"	"	0.0521	0.0305	96.60	
SnCl ₄	A pinch	Deposit crystalline, coarse and diseased spots			granular, with crevices and
SbCl ₃	"	Deposit spoiled, black, non-adherent and powdery.			
BiCl ₃	"	Deposit amorphous and adherent with "trees" forming tendency and blackening effect.			
"	In micro quantity.	Considerable improvement in the deposit.			
Gelatin	0.003 g.	0.0539 g.	0.0318 g.	95.87	Deposit white dull, amorphous, uniform and adherent.
"	"	0.0489	0.0290	95.27	
"	0.020	0.0610	0.0362	95.30	Improvement in the deposit.
"	"	0.0643	0.0378	96.20	
"	0.050	0.0591	0.0341	98.03	Further improved.
"	"	0.0691	0.0402	97.2	
"	0.10	0.0572	0.0343	94.33	Deposit further im- proved.
"	"	0.0621	0.0370	94.93	
Dextrin	0.1	0.0627	0.0368	96.37	Fine, uniform, shining, crystalline deposit; no pitting effect.
"	"	0.0813	0.0480	95.80	
"	0.25	0.0604	0.0353	96.50	Finer deposit but crystalline.
"	"	0.0625	0.0368	96.06	
"	0.50	0.0577	0.0338	96.60	Improvement in the deposit.
"	"	0.0838	0.0489	96.99	
"	1.0	0.0578	0.0400	95.90	Still improved.
"	"	0.0697	0.0412	95.70	
Glycerine	0.5 c.c.	0.0676	0.0402	95.70	Deposit not uniform, crystalline with diseased spots.
"	"	0.0501	0.0297	95.38	
"	1.0 "	0.0524	0.0318	93.30	Slight improvement in the deposit.
"	"	0.0461	0.0280	93.11	
Sucrose	5.0 g.	0.0667	0.0397	95.01	Deposit non-uniform, irregular, granular, coarse and crystalline with pitting effect and diseased spots.
"	"	0.0596	0.0357	94.41	
"	10.0	0.0578	0.0348	93.90	Not much improve- ment.
"	"	0.0608	0.0368	93.49	

DISCUSSION.

The foregoing results show that the nature and magnitude of an electrodeposit is influenced by a number of physicochemical factors. These are discussed conveniently in respect of cathode efficiency which is 100% under ideal conditions. Its diminution is chiefly due to the occurrence of side reactions, e.g. evolution of hydrogen at the cathode, or the formation of molecular or ionic complexes in the conducting mixture.

The process of electrodeposition, according to Smee, is essentially a process of crystallisation and laws of crystallisation are applicable to the electrodeposited metal. The deposition of metal consists initially of the formation of nuclei at the cathode surface followed by their growth to larger crystals. The two processes take place side by side. Each of these has a different velocity. If the velocity of (1) nuclei formation is greater than that of (2) crystal formation, a fine deposit is obtained, whereas in the reverse case the deposit is coarser and crystals big. The relation between the velocities of (1) and (2) depends, besides the factors mentioned, i.e. (a) to (f) (*vide supra*), upon (g) temperature, (h) nature of solvent, (i) nature of the metal deposited, and (j) its valency.

Our results in Table IA show that with the increase of electrode distance the deposit becomes finer. Adhesivity is also improved. From our results in Table IC it is seen that with increase in C.D., the deposit becomes finer and adherent up to a particular limit after which it shows a distinct 'tree'-forming tendency, especially at the edges. Similar were the conclusions of Wernick (*loc. cit.*) who demonstrated that the increase in C.D. decreases appreciably the grain size and improves adhesivity and burnishability of the cadmium deposit from the sulphate bath containing boric acid and sodium chloride. At C.D. above 4.5 amps. per sq. dm. he observed that the 'tree' formation was more prominent even with a violently agitated solution. Watanabe and Tsuchimolo (*J. Min. Met. Japan*, 1929, 7, 3, 34) noticed the same effect with cyanide bath and that C.D. necessary for giving good and satisfactory deposit largely depends upon the concentration of the bath. These changes in the nature of the deposit are consistent with the fact that at very low C.D. or with very dilute solutions, the discharge of metal ions occurs slowly and so the rate of crystal formation exceeds that of nuclei formation. thus resulting in a coarse and crystalline deposit. At higher C.D., the rate of nuclei formation increases and the deposit becomes finer-grained. 'Tree' formation or burning effects observed, especially at very high C.D., can be attributed either to the local impoverishment of the metal or metal ion content round the cathode surface due to rapid depletion of metal during the

electrolysis, or to the formation and subsequent inclusion in the cathode deposit, of hydroxides or basic salts of the metal due to increased alkalinity of the bath, caused by excessive hydrogen evolution.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

Our data recorded in Table II (*cf.* curve 1, Fig. 2) show that the cathode efficiency is very high even at low C.D. and in fairly high acidic media; it increases, though within very narrow limits (91.4 to 99%), continuously with the rise of C.D. possibly due to increase in hydrogen overvoltage and corresponding diminution in hydrogen evolution. The C.D., however, does not seem to have a marked influence over the cathode efficiency (*cf.* Wernick, *loc. cit.* Watanabe and Tsuchimolo, *loc. cit.*) in cadmium deposition as is noted to have in nickel deposition (results to be published shortly), where the efficiency alters within wide limits (0 to 100%). This remarkable difference in the behaviour of cadmium and nickel under low and high C.D. can be accounted for the hydrogen evolution at the cathode being usually the main cause leading to a deficit in the cathode deposit. The possibility of the hydrogen ions being discharged along with or in preference to metallic ions is dependent not only upon the relative position of the metals (such as cadmium and nickel) in the electrochemical series, and the concentration of H^+ ions and of metal ions in the electrolyte, but also upon the extent of irreversibility (Allmand and Ellingham, "Principles of Electrochemistry", 1931, p. 116) involved in the deposition of the metal and of hydrogen under any given set of conditions. Thus, though cadmium is a baser metal than nickel, yet it can be cathodically deposited from a solution containing much acid,

with high current efficiency, whereas nickel may not be deposited at all from a solution of corresponding concentration in metal ions and H^+ ions.

It is interesting to note that at constant values of C.D., concentration, temperature, etc., the deposit, which was initially bright and adherent, tends to become, as the time elapses, loose, powdery, non-adhesive and black (*cf.* Table Id). This can be attributed to the increased alkalinity of the bath due to high anodic efficiency of cadmium anode (more than 100%), with the progress of electrolysis and subsequent inclusion of the basic hydroxides in the cathode deposit. Kurda's findings (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, 178, 377) lead to similar conclusions.

Our results in Table Ix show that the addition of free sulphuric acid (N/50) to the bath solution improves considerably the nature and quality of the deposit, as examined microscopically. Increased concentration of the acid, however, besides lowering the cathode efficiency to a considerable extent (97.4 to 25.9%, *cf.* curve 1, Fig. 1) owing to excessive hydrogen evolution, gives 'cracked' and 'pitted' deposits with deep crevices. Results with the addition of Na_2SO_4 (*cf.* Table Ix) to the bath show that both the quality and quantity of the deposit get very much improved with increased amount of added material, upto 5%, and then remain almost unaffected with 10%. The sudden inflexion in the cathode efficiency-sodium sulphate concentration curve (curve 2, Fig. 1) corresponding to 5% sodium sulphate yielding smooth and satisfactory deposit, may possibly be attributed to the existence of a complex salt, $Na_2[Cd(SO_4)_2]$ in the plating solution. The solutions containing complex salts are known to give satisfactory and better deposits than those containing simple salts. The favourable results obtained can, in general, be attributed to sodium sulphate acting either as a conducting salt or as a bath stabiliser owing to its buffer action. This stabilising influence of Na_2SO_4 seems to have been noticed earlier by Westbrook (*Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1929, May, advanced copy) who concludes that various substances like $NaCN$, $NaOH$, Na_2SO_4 added to the cyanide bath increase the conductivity and stability of the bath, raise the cathodic current efficiency, throwing power and maximum C.D. for satisfactory deposition and give smoother and finer grained deposits. He further adds that the presence of Na_2SO_4 hardly affects the electrical properties of the bath but seems to render it more stable. Because of common $SO_4^{=}$ ion in $CdSO_4$, H_2SO_4 , and Na_2SO_4 the metal ion content of the bath solution is depressed to a considerably low value, a condition which is favourable for good and fine deposit.

From a study of the data, shown in Table III, it is seen that at constant C.D., the quality and quantity of the deposit (*cf.* curve 2, Fig. 2) improve

by increasing the temperature up to a certain extent (about 45°) and deteriorate at higher temperature (80°) in agreement with the earlier observations of Planner and Schlotter (*Z. Metalik.*, 1930, 22, 41). This can be explained by the fact that with the rise in temperature, the conductivity increases due to increased mobilities of the ions, with a concomitant increment in the cathode efficiency up to 45°; at higher temperatures, however, other factors, *e.g.* convection currents, lowering of hydrogen overvoltage, throwing power, etc., come into play as a result of which the efficiency diminishes.

No precise information is, however, available in the literature for the correlation of the cathode efficiency with the proportion of an addition agent in the electrolytic bath. We have studied this in greater details (*cf.* results in Table IV) in the case of various inorganic and organic agents, whose concentrations were varied, especially in a few cases over a wide range. Various theories attempting to explain the influence of addition agents, which are generally organic or colloidal substances, exist in the literature. The possible rôle of colloidal addition agents, in general, has been discussed in a review by Blum (*Colloid Symposium Monograph*, 1921, 8, 300), who suggests the following factors for cases in which the addition agent has actually been found in the cathode deposits: "(1) co-discharge of colloid particles and metal ions, (2) discharge of complex ions containing the metal and the colloid, (3) adsorption of colloid upon the face of the metal deposit, or (4) mechanical inclusion in the deposit." Blum further states in regard to these various possibilities that "it is difficult from the meagre data available to suggest the relative probabilities of these processes..." However, other workers have expressed preference for one or the other of the particular views outlined above. Thus Bancroft (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1913, 23, 266) tacitly assumes that adsorption accounts for the inclusion of the addition agent in the deposit; Fuseya and Murata, (*ibid.*, 1926, 50, 235) postulated the existence of complex cations formed from the metal ion and addition agent and produce evidence to show that such complex ions are doubtless formed (*cf.* also Marie and Buffat, *J. chim. phys.*, 1927, 24, 470; Taft and Messmore, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 36, 2585). Among the causes which normally promote the production of rough and 'treed' deposits is the presence of suspended impurities, especially, conducting particles of carbon, metal, etc. derived from the anodes. Upthegrove and Baker (*Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1928, 53, 389) have noticed that such impurities lodge themselves upon the cathode and serve as nuclei for the growth of large grained crystals or 'trees'. Much of the effect of addition agents in reducing roughness is that of counteracting the influence of suspended matter.

Our results with $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, $18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ show that the addition of this to the bath showed no marked improvement in the deposit; the cathode efficiency decreases steadily, owing to the plating out of Al along with Cd on the cathode. Inclusion of this as an addition agent in the present investigation was suggested because of its favourable effects in the deposition of Zn from zinc bath (Thompson, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1926, 80, 193) due to its buffer action and of nickel from a nickel bath (p_{H} about 5.6) as observed in these laboratories, possibly due to its hydrolysis, which commences at a p_{H} of about 5, and subsequent inclusion in the cathode deposit. Under the operating conditions of Cd-deposition from an acid bath (p_{H} about 3), $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, $18\text{H}_2\text{O}$, may not, it is anticipated, modify the structure of the deposit as its hydrolysis is arrested by the high acidity of the medium, an inference in close accord with our findings. Our results show that the addition of NiSO_4 , $7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ gives bright and smooth deposits, in agreement with the earlier observations of Westbrook (*loc. cit.*) and others, but lowers the cathode efficiency, possibly due to simultaneous deposition of Ni. The addition in traces or very little amounts of certain agents *viz.*, HgCl_2 , CrO_3 , SnCl_4 , SbCl_3 , BiCl_3 , SnO , SnO_2 , CS_2 , and pyridine gives loose, powdery, black and wholly unsatisfactory deposits. Addition of ZnSO_4 , $7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ does not show any improvement in the deposit. In presence of H_2O_2 (0.5%), the deposit gets spoiled but the cathode efficiency increases, possibly due to hydrogen evolution at the cathode being considerably arrested. A trace of SnCl_2 (0.01%), when added to the bath, shows marked improvement in the deposit; with its increased amounts (0.1%), a highly smooth, white, amorphous, adherent and fine-grained deposit is obtained. The cathode efficiency also increases. That SnCl_2 functions as the most efficient addition agent in Cd-deposition may, possibly, be attributed to its capacity to pass into a colloidal state, due to hydrolysis, as evidenced by a sudden but distinct development of opalescence in the solution, and its subsequent inclusion in the cathode deposit, where its presence hinders the crystal growth thus resulting in the formation of a fine-grained deposit. The presence of Sn in the cathode deposit was detected by usual qualitative tests. Addition of gelatin in small amounts to the bath gives smooth, amorphous and adherent deposit; with the increased amount the quality of the deposit gets further improved. The cathode efficiency increases with the increasing amount of gelatin, up to a certain limit (0.05%) and then diminishes with further addition. Similar results were also obtained with the addition of dextrin. Earlier results of Millian (*loc. cit.*) showed that smooth metallic deposits of cadmium are obtained with the addition of gelatin *only* from the solutions of strong acids as sulphates, fluosilicates or

fluoroborates. He further states that the addition of gelatin to the acid Cd-bath renders the metallic deposit more bright and increases its hardness. Our results with the gelatin may, therefore, easily be accounted for as follows. Gelatin being a complex colloid, under the operating conditions of the bath and highly favourable acidic medium (pH about 3, far below 4.7, the iso-electric point for gelatin) gets positively charged (Frolich, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 67) and migrates on electrolysis to the cathode surface and gets included in the deposit thereby affecting the crystal structure of the deposit by minimising the grain size. The maximum values for cathodic efficiencies in the presence of 0.05% gelatin and 0.5% dextrin, may possibly be attributed to the discharge at the cathode of the complex cations of the metal with the addition agent of the type, $[Cd-n(\text{gelatin})]^{++}$ $[Cd-n(\text{dextrin})]^{++}$. Further evidence in favour of such a possibility, especially in the deposition of silver and copper, can be adduced from the earlier communications (*cf.* Joshi, Solanki and Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 174; Joshi and Padmanabhan, *ibid*, 1938, 15, 185) from these laboratories. Addition of glycerine (upto 1%) and sucrose (upto 10%) to the bath, gives wholly unsatisfactory deposits (results in Table IV), possibly due to increased resistance of the bath solution.

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ELECTROCHEMISTRY SECTION, CHEMICAL
LABORATORIES, THE HINDU
UNIVERSITY, BENARES.

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